

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPING SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF GRADUATE STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: In this thesis, opinions are given about the theoretical foundations of education of social and cultural competence of the students of the graduating class based on the gender approach.

Key words: educational system, gender socialization, value, gender approach, social culture.

One of the important directions of the development of pedagogical sciences at the current stage of education is the formation of a new field of scientific knowledge that studies the specific features of teaching and educating children of different genders - the formation of gender pedagogy. The subject of studying gender pedagogy is correcting the process of socialization of the young generation depending on gender in the period of global socio-economic and cultural changes. The importance of reforming the education system taking into account gender approaches is indicated in the gender strategy of education.

Educational institutions, in turn, reflect the gender stratification of society and culture as a whole, demonstrating the unequal status of men and women. The most important goal of gender education is to deconstruct the traditional cultural limitations of the development of individual potential depending on gender, to create conditions for boys and girls to realize themselves as much as possible in the process of pedagogical interaction. Its development allows the formation of the opinion that gender relations are not grounds for discrimination in any sphere of life, and allows school graduates to freely choose the methods and forms of self-realization.

The gender approach involves the harmonization of gender interaction based on egalitarianism as the principle of equal rights and opportunities for individuals regardless of their gender. Implementation of the gender approach in the social and cultural education of students of the graduating class means putting the personality and individuality of students above the traditional framework of gender in the process of development and education.

The gender approach in direct perception is aimed at creating such conditions for the upbringing of boys and girls with social and cultural characteristics, their "development and spiritual-value direction individual male , promotes the manifestation and positive formation of feminine and androgynous characteristics, painless adaptation of the young generation to the reality of gender relations in society, and gender flexibility in society".

In general, pedagogy and education, as a pedagogical phenomenon, according to L. B. Shtileva, students need to understand their approach to gender socio-cultural issues, because the strict standards repeated by the school in terms of femininity and masculinity make students becomes an objective obstacle for effective socialization.

The development of gender education is necessary to ensure the national security of the country: the country cannot ignore or underutilize the potential of any gender in all spheres of life. The state's equal rights policy is based on the gender model of symmetrical and balanced inclusion of men and women in all spheres of social life. Therefore, it is vital and important to develop and implement a gender-neutral approach in education based on comprehensive consideration of the interests of both socio-gender groups of society.

The essence of the gender approach in education is an individual approach to the manifestation of the child's gender identity. From the point of view of this approach, gender identity is the same, not fixed, the same for all men and women within their gender, the plurality, individuality, and plasticity of gender differences are recognized. This means that education faces the task of individualizing gender identity and studying the subjective meanings of creating one or another identity model by each student.

Thus, one of the tasks of introducing a gender approach to education is to create conditions for the growth of self-awareness and self-awareness of a person with an individual set of masculine, feminine and androgynous characteristics. is to create opportunities. According to L. B. Shtileva, effective implementation of the gender approach to education, "studying the factors of the pedagogical environment that affect the process of forming the gender identity of students, the forms of school work that are important for gender social and cultural development, for this, it is necessary to train pedagogical staff.

Therefore, understanding the problems of social and cultural education of the students of the graduating class on the basis of gender, mastering the basic rules of the concept of gender is becoming an urgent task in the field of education and training of young people, as well as in the field of training

specialists who are professionally engaged in gender education. In terms of age, according to I. Kostikova, gender education should be considered as the education of social and cultural characteristics of students of the school graduating class.¹ Education should be aimed at helping them with socialization problems, an important component of which is identifying the child as a boy or a girl and accepting a certain social role by them.

Gender education of teachers of the graduate class provides an understanding of the specific characteristics of the growth of boys and girls and is aimed at overcoming stereotypes that hinder the successful development of the child's personality. Specific features of education imply a theoretical direction, its orientation to the discussion of fundamental problems in the field of gender approaches in education.

The teaching style and forms of communication in the graduate class also affect the education of gender social and cultural characteristics of students. Thus, examinations in the form of tests, individual reports, and selections for grades primarily stimulate the development of masculine qualities. Both boys and girls suffer because their critical thinking skills, the ability to ask questions, and the ability to discuss problems together are less developed in them.

In connection with the tasks defined in the gender strategy of the educational system, there is a need to introduce pedagogical concepts aimed at understanding the positions of individuals in the issues of gender socialization into the curriculum. In the same process, implicit learning democracy and humanitarian characteristics can be changed. M. Jenkins has developed tips for teachers who want to create an environment of tolerance and equality in their classes. To this end, the author created a checklist that includes introspection of lectures and course content taught, as well as interactions in the classroom.

The structure of the educational module is represented by two main sections: the problem of the gender approach to the education of students' social and cultural characteristics in education and the problem of the formation of gender tolerance of schoolchildren. The content of the program covers the following issues: the essence of gender concepts, the development of a person's gender identity, gender approaches in education, the problem of teaching boys and girls together and separately, gender socialization of students.

In conclusion, to improve the skills of the students of the graduating class on gender issues in the education of social and cultural characteristics, to regularly

¹ Kostikova, I., Mitrofanova, A., Pulina, N., Gradskova, Yu. Prospects for gender education in Russia 2001. - No. 2. – C. b8 – 75.

provide them with information, to equip them with educational manuals, as well as to promote the theoretical and methodological foundations of gender knowledge, helps implement the gender strategy, promote the ideas of gender equality in society.

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